

DEVELOPING OF READING STRATEGIES IN EFL CLASSES

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ABSTRACT: Teaching or learning a foreign language is not an easy matter as it requires much attempt as well as working hard. Reading is a crucial part of teaching a language as it demonstrates the main meaning of a language. By reading, one can imagine the concept and realizes the situation as well as has a reply for it. In order to develop reading skills in EFL classes, educators can utilize various types of methods to improve pupils' knowledge. The purpose of the article is to research on reading types and reading strategies. Moreover, the following thesis illustrates the historical background of reading and some strategies to get students' abilities improved.

KEY WORDS: reading, intensive reading, extensive reading, skimming, scanning, reading strategies, syntactic, semantic, phonological system.

“Reading” can be defined that, it is process of looking at a range of written materials, symbols and as a result getting meaning from these sources. When you read, you use your eyes to receive written symbols like letters, punctuation marks and spaces and you can use your brain to convert them into words, sentences and paragraphs that communicate something to each other. Reading is considered a mental ability, and it can be said that the symbols and signs he sees are printed on paper. The learning process can start from the age of 4 or 5 years. Because children at this age can easily distinguish the objects around them, remember their names and repeat them. Therefore, it can be said that any child can learn to read from the youngest age. However, this requires the teacher to show the right direction and take into account every ability of the child.

The first written communication dates all the way back to the far history, 3500 B.C., when only a few number of people learned to read and write. In those days, people who knew how to read held public performances, displaying their skill. It wasn't for several thousand years that the first books came on the scene. Originally the first reading material dates back to the 8th century when people began to get knowledge on literacy skills. First written works existed on the surface of stones and rocks of caves. The 18th century was the beginning of a major iron works in the town and the growth of the brewing trade for which reading became common among people. Over time, literacy skills have become an integral part of human life, and today reading and writing skills are a necessity not only for intellectuals, but also for ordinary workers and farmers.

Reading is a process of understanding and comprehending is important when a foreign language is taught. There are different types of reading and they are as the following:

1) Skimming – it is sometimes referred to as gist reading, means going through the text to grasp the basic idea. It is a strategic as well as selective type of reading method. learners focus on the main ideas of a text in it. When skimming, deliberately skip text that provides details, stories, data, or other elaboration. Instead of closely reading every word, focus on the introduction, chapter summaries, beginning and ending sentences of paragraphs, bold words, and text features. Skimming is extracting the essence of the author's main messages. In this case, we may have a question, why learners should skim the text instead of full reading. There are some factors for that. Learners **should have a big imagination or main points when they are reading a text.** Even if pupils are going to do a detailed reading of the text, skimming can help them to comprehend well what they read, as a form of previewing. Being aware of skimming will help you to become more efficient, strategic and smart reader. Learners or pupils will become better at determining what parts of the text are most important with the help of this reading type. Sometimes students are required to understand the big picture, not all of the little details. In these case, skimming helps them to understand the overall points of the text and its relevance to course without bogging down. Moreover, it makes the most of time, since sometimes we do not have to do everything. With the help of skimming, reader can be able to cover their valuable time vast amounts of material more quickly and save time for everything else. In this case, skimming assists to get main points and attend class much more.

2) Scanning is another type of reading which can be mentioned essential like scanning as it gives main meaning of a text. Scanning is an important reading technique which is reading fast in order to find specific fact being based on numbers, dates and other facts in discourse. Differ from skimming; scanning helps readers locate a particular fact. Skimming is like snorkeling, and scanning is like pearl diving. Scanning also economizes readers' time as its purpose is to find main data about the topic.

3) Intensive reading is another type of reading which is far more time economizing rather that skimming and scanning. It needs all the attention of a reader to get details. This type of reading involves close reading which purposes at the accuracy of understanding. In this method reader has to comprehend the meaning of each word. Mostly this type of reading is used in the first stages of

learning or teaching I EFL classes as it is essential to know all the terms and words as well as phrases meaning and to enlarge the vocabulary of a speaker. On the other hand, most readers find it boring and difficult to read intensively, however, according to my 6 years experience of learning a foreign language, I assume that intensive reading plays an essential role in the studying process.

4) Extensive reading is an interesting way of reading and understanding of a discourse. This type of reading lays more emphasis on fluency rather than accuracy and it is often involved reading for pleasure as well as it is chosen by readers, themselves or their parents according to their age, interest or career. It lays more emphasis on fluency and less accuracy. Moreover, it is done out of classroom. Eventually, some students do it as their hobbies. It is free reading just to improve readers' integrated skills.

Apart from types, reading models are indicated by two basic theories of psycholinguistics models and schema theory models. The psycholinguistics models proposed by a scholar, Goodman put their framework on the perceptual process. In addition the schema theory emphasizes its functional work in the role of background knowledge.

1. The first reading model which is being mentioned as "psycholinguistic model of reading", during the past decade, EFL reading theory has come under the influence of psycholinguistics' and Goodman's psycholinguistics model of reading. Goodman illustrated the process of reading as a "psycholinguistic guessing game". This model promotes that in reading, the reader reconstructs a message which has been encoded by a writer as a graphic show.

2. The next reading model is schema theory model which is based on theoretical concept of reading. According to Bartlett, 1932; Rumerlhart and Ortony, 1977; Rumerlhart, 1980, the role of background knowledge in language understanding and comprehending it, has been formalized as schema theory. It is a theory that suggests a passage providing directions for readers how to construct meaning in their mind, previously acquired knowledge and it is called the reader's background knowledge. According to this theory, comprehension is an interactive process between reader's background knowledge and new text information. Effective comprehension requires the ability related to the textual material to one person's own knowledge. Understanding words, phrases, sentences and entire text involves much more rather than just relying on one person's linguistic knowledge. Furthermore, the process of interpretation is guided by the principle that every input is mapped

against some existing schema and that all aspects of that schema must be compatible with the input information. As a result, these principles in two basic modes of information have two processes: bottom-up and top-down processing. Vitaly essential aspect of top-down and bottom-up processing is both occur at all levels simultaneously.

Here some scanning features are given to focus on well:

- Introduction and conclusion
- Chapter summaries
- First and last sentences
- Titles, subtitles, and headings, subheadings
- Bold words
- Charts, graphs, or pictures
- End of chapter review questions

To sum up all, EFL classes refer to the educational situation of teaching as well as learning as a foreign language. Having EFL lessons in our country, Uzbekistan is becoming widened. Moreover, EFL classes are educational setting where English is taught to people whose native language is not English and they are in a country where English is not an official language. For example, a class where Uzbek students learn English in Uzbekistan.

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